

Relationship Between the Absence of Community Support and Psychological Trauma in Conflicts: A Case Study of IDPs in Cabo Delgado

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ABSTRACT

Background: Violent extremism in Cabo Delgado, Mozambique, has resulted in the displacement of over one million individuals. Internally displaced persons (IDPs), especially children, women, and individuals with disabilities, face severe psychological trauma compounded by the absence of community support, resulting from poverty. **Objective:** To explore the relationship between the absence of community support and the psychological trauma experienced by IDPs in Cabo Delgado, with the aim of identifying critical needs for effective mental health and peacebuilding interventions. **Method:** This qualitative study involved semi-structured interviews with 26 IDPs from Cabo Delgado. Participants included men and women aged 12 to 63 years, all of whom had fled during or following a terrorist attack. Thematic analysis was used to examine participants' experiences of trauma, post-traumatic growth, coping mechanisms, and perceptions of community support. **Results:** Among participants, 66.7% exhibited trauma symptoms, while 33.3% demonstrated post-traumatic growth. The absence of community support, combined with financial instability and material losses, exacerbated psychological distress. Key themes included grief, loss, and limited access to resources. Despite these challenges, some participants reported resilience through spiritual beliefs and interpersonal relationships. **Conclusions:** The findings highlight the urgent need for systemic, culturally sensitive mental health interventions that address both individual trauma and the broader socioeconomic vulnerabilities faced by IDPs. Strengthening community support mechanisms is essential for fostering resilience and promoting recovery.

Keywords: *Cabo Delgado, internally displaced persons, psychological trauma, psychosocial support, community support, Mozambique, violent extremism*

1 INTRODUCTION

Poverty is a multifaceted issue that requires complex models for effective mitigation, addressing the interplay of various social, economic, political, and environmental factors from macro to micro levels. The Quadruple Helix Model proposed by Dinata (2023) involves collaboration among academia, industry, government, and civil society, emphasising communalism and social resilience in handling poverty in rural communities. In healthcare, this model can help create solidarity among different stakeholders to address health issues effectively, enhancing healthcare delivery and access in rural communities (Dinata, 2023).

Poverty in Africa remains a significant challenge despite some improvements over the years. The continent has the highest number of extremely poor individuals globally, with over 70% of the world's poorest people residing in Africa (Becker & Frankema, 2019). While the percentage of the African population living in poverty declined from 56.8% to 42.7% between 1990 and 2012 (Omomowo, 2018), progress has been slow and poverty levels remain higher than in other developing regions (Anakudo & Ezenekwe, 2022). Factors contributing to poverty in Africa include rapid population growth, inefficient

agricultural practices, diseases like AIDS and malaria, the COVID-19 pandemic, poor governance, and conflicts (Beegle & Christiaensen, 2019).

The poverty situation in Mozambique is complex and multifaceted. Research indicates a halt in the reduction of multidimensional poverty between 2015 and 2018, leading to an increase in the number of poor people, particularly in rural areas and central provinces (Egger, Salvucci & Tarp, 2023). Mozambique's economy accelerated in 2023, with real GDP growth expected to reach 5.3% (UNICEF – Mozambique, 2024). Vulnerability to poverty remains high, especially in rural northern and central regions, with significant risks of downward mobility even for non-poor households (Salvucci & Tarp, 2021). Child multidimensional poverty is prevalent: 81% of children experience deprivation in at least two dimensions, with higher vulnerability in rural areas and provinces such as Niassa, Zambezia, and Cabo Delgado (Ferrone, Rossi & Brukauf, 2019).

Despite its mineral wealth, Mozambique faces significant poverty challenges. The Family Budget Enquiry 2022, which interviewed 15,000 families, revealed that the richest 10% account for 40% of expenditures, while the poorest 10% represent only 1% (Instituto Nacional de Estatística, 2023). On average, every family spends only USD 135 per month, ranging from USD 196 in cities to USD 104 in rural areas, and the unemployment rate stands at 18% (Instituto Nacional de Estatística, 2023). The country was a Portuguese colony until independence on 25 June 1975, and endured a civil war between FRELIMO and RENAMO from 1977 to 1992; the DDR process concluded only in June 2023.

Cabo Delgado Province, the country's richest in minerals but poorest in income, has been afflicted by violent extremism since October 2017. From October 2017 to 26 May 2024, 1,832 incidents of organised violence were reported, resulting in 5,712 deaths, including 2,379 civilian fatalities, and causing around 1,028,743 IDPs (Cabo Ligado, 2024; IOM, 2023). IDPs, particularly children, adolescents, and women with disabilities, need special attention for trauma-related disorders (WHO, 2011). Over 779,000 children need humanitarian protection services, and over 1,900 children are unaccompanied or separated from their families (UNICEF – Mozambique).

Trauma in its various forms — individual, community, and intergenerational — is prevalent in the Mozambican population, which has experienced violence for centuries. Trauma-related disorders and psychological vulnerability are risk factors for radicalisation, especially in areas lacking mental health professionals trained in trauma intervention and the prevention of violent extremism (Radicalisation Awareness Network, 2019). There is an urgent need to increase structured mental health responses for IDPs, including community resilience mechanisms, cultural rituals, and social cohesion approaches (Inter-Agency Standing Committee, 2007).

To address this complex issue, a comprehensive, systemic approach must target risk factors for joining violent extremist movements while promoting social resilience and positive peace — enhancing the skills of mental health professionals, increasing local service capacity, promoting gender equality, and involving local leadership and civil society (Mota & Canuma, 2024; Rodrigues, 2012; Lederach, 1999). Having that in mind, the primary aim of this study was to explore the relationship between the absence of community support and the psychological trauma experienced by IDPs in Cabo Delgado, and to identify critical needs for effective mental health and peacebuilding interventions.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Design

The study employed a qualitative exploratory approach, using a semi-structured interview script based on Hobfoll's Principles for crisis intervention, attending to the ongoing armed conflict context the participants were in.

2.2 Participants

Twenty-six IDPs from Cabo Delgado province in Mozambique participated in the study. The sample consisted of 20 females and 6 males, with a mean age of 30 years (median: 28; range: 12–63). Participants were from the districts of Palma, Quissanga, Muidumbe, Mocímboa da Praia, and Macomia, and had fled following or during a terrorist attack.

Inclusion criteria were: (a) individuals displaced within Cabo Delgado due to conflict and violence, including survivors of terrorist attacks, individuals deprived of their freedom, girls and women who experienced sexual violence or forced marriage, and boys coerced into training with terrorist groups. Exclusion criteria were: (a) individuals not internally displaced due to conflict in Cabo Delgado; (b) children under 10 years old; and (c) individuals who declined or were unable to provide informed consent.

2.3 Data Collection

Data collection took place through interviews conducted in the districts of Chiúre, Ancuabe, Metuge, and Pemba during July–October 2021. A cultural mediator assisted the interviews, translating between Portuguese, Makua, Makonde, and Mwani to allow participants to express themselves freely.

2.4 Procedure

Interviews were conducted in a private and confidential setting to encourage openness and trust. The interviewer was trained in trauma-informed approaches to ensure sensitivity and ethical conduct throughout the process. Qualitative data from interviews were transcribed and analysed thematically. Themes focused on experiences of psychological trauma, coping mechanisms, community support, and perceptions of terrorism.

2.5 Ethics Statement

Prior to interviews, oral (recorded) consent was obtained from each participant or their legal guardian. Written consent was not collected due to the ongoing armed conflict, in order to protect the safety of participants. All data were treated with strict confidentiality and stored securely in accordance with ethical guidelines. Each interview session incorporated Psychological First Aid techniques.

3 RESULTS

All participants had fled their homes as a result of terrorist attacks. Among the respondents, 33.3% showed signs of post-traumatic growth, primarily attributed to spiritual experiences and interpersonal relationships. Additionally, 80% of the participants reported significant losses, including material possessions, bereavement, and instances of disappearances.

The analysis of the interviews revealed several key themes related to the psychological impact of displacement, loss, and ongoing conflict, as well as the coping mechanisms adopted by the participants. The findings are summarised in Table 1, which outlines the main categories and subcategories, along with the percentage of participants who discussed each theme.

TABLE 1 | Main categories, sub-categories and quotes from IDPs in Cabo Delgado.

Main Category	Subcategory	Quotes
Support	Social and Humanitarian	"Per day, 10 kilograms of rice are used, but only one person was listed to receive the food, and it's not enough for 20 people." (Participant 1)
		"We haven't received anything, my sister-in-law just wrote but her name isn't on the list, and mine isn't either." (Participant 2)
		"We need more help; my whole family is here, and my sister-in-law has grandchildren. We need assistance." (Participant 2)
Support	Financial	"I am suffering; my husband is unemployed, and we are struggling a

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		lot." (Participant 5)
		"We are living in borrowed houses, and we don't have clothes or food." (Participant 4)
		"It's difficult here, I have no means, no work, no way to support my children." (Participant 8)
	Resources	"I tried saving, picking things from the beach to eat, but there's nothing here." (Participant 8)
		"I can't even find a place to sleep here; the conditions are terrible." (Participant 9)
		"The house is falling apart, and I have no way to fix it. We don't have the means to improve anything." (Participant 9)
Loss	Grief (Death)	"My family lost five people in the conflict." (Participant 1)
		"Yes, they burned everything, and my uncle's son was killed." (Participant 8)
		"The loss of family members has left a big hole in our hearts." (Participant 4)
	Disappearances	"My husband was unreachable for several days, and I didn't know if he was alive or dead." (Participant 7)
		"My sister-in-law and her children were missing for 22 days, and we didn't know whether they were dead or alive." (Participant 2)
		"I lost contact with my family for months, and every day was a struggle, not knowing what had happened to them." (Participant 3)
	Material Loss	"The house was burned down; we left with nothing, just a shirt." (Participant 2)
		"We lost everything, all our belongings were destroyed. It's hard to rebuild from nothing." (Participant 8)
		"We lost our home, all our possessions; we started from scratch when we arrived here." (Participant 1)
Future	Need for Support/Help	"We are living in other people's homes, and we don't know how to manage. If I had a job, I could forget about the war." (Participant 8)
		"I need work to take care of my children. Without help, we are just surviving, not living." (Participant 3)
		"I don't have anything here. I need a job, some means to support my family." (Participant 4)
	Return vs Not Returning to their Land	"I don't want to go back, I prefer staying here." (Participant 1)
		"I'll return when the war is over, but right now, I can't. It's too dangerous." (Participant 8)
		"I'm unsure. I would like to go back home, but there's so much fear. I don't know if it's safe yet." (Participant 3)
	Plans for the Future	"I would like to have a job and a secure place for my family." (Participant 6)
		"I want to have a stable life again, a house, and the opportunity to work and support my children." (Participant 2)
		"I want to open a small business to support my family, and give my children the opportunity to study." (Participant 9)
Attack	Characteristics of the Attack	"They came on motorbikes, and there were many armed men." (Participant 1)
		"The attackers were ruthless; they took everything, including our dignity." (Participant 3)
		"They arrived in the middle of the night, shooting and shouting. It was chaos." (Participant 8)
	Escape	"We fled into the bush, and my husband stayed behind because he was sick." (Participant 1)

Attack	Escape	"I ran with my children, we didn't know where we were going, but we had to escape." (Participant 2)
		"We left everything behind, only took what we could carry, and ran as fast as we could." (Participant 3)
	Feelings about the Attack/Memories	"I was scared, thinking I might die like others did." (Participant 3)
		"I think about what happened every night. The screams, the violence. It's hard to forget." (Participant 1)
		"When I remember what happened, I feel like I can't breathe. The memories suffocate me." (Participant 8)
Signs of Growth	Psychological Factors/Personality	"I'm stronger than this, I've already been through much." (Participant 2)
		"I've learned to adapt. I no longer worry as much. I focus on surviving day by day." (Participant 6)
		"I try to stay positive, I know I can't change the past, so I focus on building a future for my children." (Participant 3)
	Beliefs/Religion	"I believe that God will help me overcome all this." (Participant 3)
		"I've learned that only God can give me the strength to go on." (Participant 6)
		"When everything seemed lost, I turned to God, and it gave me peace." (Participant 7)
	Coping Strategies	"I try to stay occupied by doing small tasks to find food and keep my mind off things." (Participant 1)
		"I focus on my children's needs, that keeps me going." (Participant 8)
		"I started working again, even though it's not much. It helps me forget, even if just for a moment." (Participant 9)
Risk Factors for Trauma	Presence of Symptoms (Pre, Peri, and Post-Traumatic)	"I feel very anxious, I get physical symptoms like high blood pressure from thinking too much." (Participant 1)
		"I'm afraid every time I hear loud noises or see motorbikes. It brings back the memories." (Participant 8)
		"I've been feeling overwhelmed with fear; I get nightmares and flashbacks often." (Participant 3)
	Biological Factors	"When I think of what I've lost, I feel physical pain." (Participant 4)
		"My body aches when I think about the past, and it's hard to function." (Participant 2)
		"I feel tense and exhausted all the time, like my body hasn't recovered from everything." (Participant 8)
	Psychological Factors	"I cry a lot, my mind is full of thoughts I can't forget." (Participant 7)
		"I feel like I'm trapped in my thoughts. I can't escape them." (Participant 3)
		"I can't sleep. I keep hearing the screams from the attack." (Participant 9)

3.1 Support Needs and Humanitarian Assistance

A recurring theme was the need for humanitarian aid, with 27% of participants highlighting insufficient support in terms of food and resources. Financial instability, affecting 46.7% of the respondents, was another major issue, reflecting the widespread difficulty in meeting basic needs.

3.2 Loss and Psychological Impact

Loss emerged as a central theme, with 80% of participants discussing the emotional toll of losing family members, possessions, and homes. The grief associated with these losses was compounded by the uncertainty and fear surrounding missing loved ones.

3.3 Future Outlook and the Need for Support

Approximately 80% of participants expressed a need for ongoing support to cope with their current situation. While some participants expressed a desire to return to their homeland after the conflict, others feared continued violence and instability. Plans for the future varied, with many focusing on the need for work and a stable environment to support their families.

3.4 Experiences of the Attack

All participants reported direct encounters with the attackers, with a common theme of violence and fear. The attacks were described as chaotic and terrifying, and many participants discussed the impact of these experiences on their mental health, particularly the uncertainty of family members' survival.

3.5 Signs of Post-Traumatic Growth

Despite the traumatic experiences, 33.3% of participants demonstrated signs of psychological resilience. They shared how they had adapted to their new circumstances, developing coping strategies such as focusing on day-to-day survival and finding meaning in their struggles.

3.6 Risk Factors for Trauma and Psychological Symptoms

The psychological impact of the trauma was evident in the symptoms reported by 60% of the participants, including anxiety, insomnia, and physical manifestations such as high blood pressure. These symptoms reflect the ongoing mental health challenges faced by displaced populations.

4 DISCUSSION

The findings of this study align with recent research indicating that approximately 70% of respondents exhibit signs of psychological distress, consistent with studies conducted during the pandemic. In our study, 60% of participants reported experiencing symptoms indicative of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), including anxiety, insomnia, and somatic complaints. The perception of inadequate support, compounded by the uncertainty regarding the whereabouts of missing family members and the persistent armed conflict, has significantly hindered efforts to minimise the trauma's impact. As evidenced in Table 1, 27% of participants reported insufficient humanitarian aid, and 46.7% highlighted financial instability as a major source of distress. These factors underscore the importance of providing psychosocial support with therapeutic objectives rather than fixed timelines, especially given the prolonged nature of the trauma, such as abductions, sexual violence, forced training, and the loss of immediate family members.

Several limitations and challenges were identified throughout the study. The colonial legacy continues to influence present-day challenges, creating a complex backdrop for intervention efforts in conflict zones like Cabo Delgado. This historical context contributes to the vulnerability of displaced populations, as it affects social structures, governance, and the overall mental health landscape. Additionally, unfamiliarity with local languages poses significant barriers to communication, impacting the effectiveness of mental health interventions. Many of the participants, particularly those from rural areas, expressed difficulty accessing aid, which is further complicated by logistical constraints and ongoing security concerns. These challenges are reflected in the data, where 60% of participants reported feelings of isolation and a lack of resources to rebuild their lives.

Moreover, the lack of understanding of cultural healing rituals limits the ability of interventions to provide holistic support tailored to the community's specific needs. Cultural intelligence is essential for engaging

effectively with displaced populations, yet it remains an area requiring improvement. Low mental health literacy, as indicated by 40% of participants who expressed difficulty in accessing support, further exacerbates the problem, as individuals are often unaware of the mental health services available to them.

The short timelines of intervention projects often fail to address the long-term psychological needs of the affected populations. As seen in the findings, many participants expressed frustration over the inability to plan for the future, with 80% of respondents highlighting the necessity of ongoing assistance. Distrust towards external interventions also complicates community engagement, as effective engagement is necessary for building sustainable support systems. Lastly, the frequent movements of IDPs, as reported by 80% of participants, add a layer of complexity to providing sustained and effective support, as constant relocation hinders access to continuous care.

These challenges underscore the importance of culturally sensitive, long-term psychosocial interventions that can adapt to the evolving needs of displaced populations in conflict zones like Cabo Delgado. Effective interventions must be flexible, community-driven, and supported by ongoing humanitarian efforts. By addressing both the immediate and long-term psychological needs, it will be possible to reduce the impact of trauma and promote recovery and resilience among those affected by displacement.

Data Availability Statement

Due to ethical considerations, the data underlying this study are not publicly available. The dataset contains sensitive and personally identifiable information collected from internally displaced persons in a conflict-affected region. Disclosure of these data could compromise the privacy, safety, and well-being of the participants. Access to the data is therefore restricted in accordance with ethical guidelines and the informed consent obtained from the participants.

Ethics Statement

The studies involving human participants were reviewed and conducted in accordance with ethical guidelines for research in conflict-affected settings. Oral recorded consent was obtained from each participant or their legal guardian prior to data collection. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Author Contributions

AIM: conceptualisation, methodology, data collection, formal analysis, writing – original draft. CSC: conceptualisation, writing – review and editing. FB: data collection, writing – review and editing. SW: data collection, writing – review and editing. All authors contributed to the article and approved the submitted version.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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